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Incorporation of Whey Water in Sugar, Palm Jaggery and Jaggery Syrup and its Acceptability

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Abstract

Milk whey is one of the highly nutritious by-products obtained from the dairy industry and left unused over years and years. The study aims to formulate the proportion of whey and sugar syrups for best sensory quality and to maximize the utilization of whey protein and an effective substitute for water in the preparation of different syrups. The whey water has been isolated from the milk by using 10% citric acid and the clarified and processed whey has been used to formulate nine syrups with varying levels of whey and sugar, jaggery and palm jaggery in 25%, 50% and 100% respectively. Finally, the formulated samples have been analyzed for sensory characteristics using descriptive statistical methods. The overall mean acceptability and SD for sugar syrup is 8.04 ± 0.63 , 7.8 ± 0.79 and 7.9 ± 0.79 respectively. For Jaggery syrup it is 8.5 ± 0.81 , 7.6 ± 1.04 and 7.2 ± 1.3 and for palm jaggery syrup, it is 8.1 ± 0.8 , 8.1 ± 0.9 and 8.3 ± 0.8 . 25% incorporation of whey is more highly acceptable in sensory characteristics, among all the syrups. The sugar syrup forms the base for beverages and sweets, it's incorporation with whey water would show significant increase in protein content of the foods.

Key words: Whey protein, Value addition, Jaggery

Milk whey is one of the highly nutritious by-products obtained from the dairy industry and left unused over years and years. Whey was discovered about 3000 years ago. Apart from being valued as a medicinal agent in the 17th and 18th centuries, whey has primarily been considered a waste by the dairy industry, and thus destined for the 'cheapest gutter'. In the late 20th century, regulations prevented disposal of untreated whey. At the same time, recognition of the value of whey components accelerated. Modern science has unraveled the secrets of whey proteins and other components, and established a sound basis for their nutritional and functional value. In parallel, technology developments exploited this underpinning knowledge, manifested as advanced whey-processing regimes. These advances have continued through the early 21st century with the focus more on the biological functionality of whey components. This whey water contains all the essential amino acids, so it was called as Complete protein. Essential amino acids present in whey water has highly biological value when comparing to other complete proteins. (Farnfield, 2009). Due to multi-nutritional benefits it was used for more therapeutic treatments. It also used by the bodybuilders and athletes who need more amount of protein in their diet. (Gangurde, 2011) Besides the nutritional properties, the whey proteins have functional properties which impart beneficial physical properties when used as ingredients in food (Minj, 2020), mainly due to its high solubility, water absorption, gelatinization and emulsifying capacities. (Ha, 2003). In this study, the whey water has been

extracted from the standardized milk and it was incorporated into Sugar syrup, Jaggery syrup and palm jaggery syrup at different proportions. Sugar syrup is a sweetener, preservative widely used in food industries and it has major role in preparation of sweets in various occasions and festivals of India and other countries. Meanwhile it was consumed by various age group people. When we add the whey water, its nutritional quality will be increased. The study aims to formulate whey water incorporated sugar syrup, jaggery syrup and palm jaggery syrup by different proportions This study focus to maximize the utilization of whey protein and an effective substitute for water in the preparation of different syrups. Whey water is functional food and it has lactoferrin, betalactoglobulin, alpha-lactalbumin, glycomacropeptide, and immunoglobulins, demonstrate a range of immune-enhancing properties. (Kareb, 2019) In addition, whey has the ability to act as an antioxidant, antihypertensive, antitumor, hypolipidemic, antiviral, antibacterial, and chelating agent. Due to fermentation the whey water also has some probiotic activity (Turkmen, 2019), so it prevents the heart related diseases. The chief amino acids present in whey syrup is cysteine to glutathione. This formulated whey syrup will be useful to eradicate the malnutrition.

Objectives:

- This study aims,
- to isolate whey water from standardized milk.

- to incorporate the whey water in sugar, palm jaggery and jaggery in different proportion.
- to find out the acceptability of formulated different proportions of whey water in sugar, palm jaggery and jaggery syrups through sensory evaluation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study has the following materials and Methodology:

Materials

- Measuring Cup
- Weighing Scale
- Standardized Milk
- Citric acid
- Sugar, Jaggery and Palm Sugar
- Muslin Cloth
- Storage Glass Container

Measuring Cup

1000 ml Moulded in Polypropylene Measuring Cup was used to measure water and milk it was bought from local super market.

Weighing Scale

Potable Electronic weighing scale (mg) was used to weighing citric acid, sugar, jaggery and palm jaggery.

Standardized Milk

From nearby aavin milk booth standardized milk was brought for the isolation of whey water.

Citric acid

Bakers citric acid was used to coagulation of milk and it was obtained from the nearest super market.

Sugar, Jaggery and Palm Jaggery

These are ingredient used for the preparation syrups granulated sugar, jaggery and palm jaggery was bought from the nearest store. Jaggery and palm Jaggery powderer was prepared by using smasher on granulated jaggery and plam jaggery.

Muslin Cloth

For the filtration of prepared whey weater incorporated syrups fresh muslin cloth was used.

Storage Glass Container

Fresh Glass Container was used store the prepared whey water incorporated syrups.

Methodology

- Isolation the whey water from Standardized Milk
- Incorporate the whey water in Sugar, jaggery and palm jaggery syrups in various proportion
- Sensory Analysis the formulated whey water incorporated syrups
- Analyze the standard deviation of sensory evaluation of whey water incorporated syrups.

Isolation the whey water

The collected standardized milk subjected into the boiling process and add citric acid. When Whole milk coagulated the substances was filtered by the strainer. The isolated whey water is stored in sterilized glass bottle.

Incorporate the whey water in Sugar, jaggery and palm jaggery syrups in various proportion

The isolated whey water was incorporated is sugar, jaggery and palm jaggery syrup by different proportions as follows.

Table 1 Preparation of whey water incorporated sugar, Jaggery and palm Jaggery syrups

S.No	Ingredients	Sugar			Jaggery			Palm Jaggery		
		SV1	SV2	SV3	JV1	JV2	JV3	PV1	PV2	PV3
1.	Water (ml)	75	50	-	75	50	-	75	50	-
2.	Whey Water (ml)	25	50	100	25	50	100	25	50	100
3.	Sugar (g)	100	100	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	Jaggey (g)	-	-	-	100	100	100	-	-	-
5.	Palm Jaggey (g)	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	100	100

Sensory Analysis of the formulated whey water incorporated syrups

The formulated whey syrup subjected into the sensory analysis by the semi trained panel members of The Standard Fireworks Rajaratnam College for Women, Sivakasi. The formulated samples were sensorically evaluated on the following sensory characteristics like colour, appearance, consistency, flavor, taste and over all acceptance on 9-point hedonic rating scale. The panel members gave ratings according their preferences. The coded samples were randomly presented to them for evaluation.

Statistical analysis

The mean and standard deviation of the different variation of the samples were analyzed through the statistical calculation in SPSS. The results are presented as follows.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sensory Analysis the formulated whey water incorporated syrups

Formulated whey water incorporated syrups were subjected into sensory evaluation by untrained panel members and mean score was found out and statistically analyzed. The whey water has been isolated from the milk by using 10% citric

acid and processed whey has been used to formulate nine syrups with varying levels of whey and sugar, jaggery and palm jaggery in 25%, 50% and 100% respectively. Finally, the formulated samples have been analyzed for sensory characteristics using descriptive statistical methods and its values are listed in (Table 2-4).

<i>Whey water incorporated sugar syrup</i>	Colour	Appearance	Consistency	Flavour	Taste	Over all Acceptance
<i>Variation I</i>	8.25 ± 0.25	8 ± 0.12	7.75 ± 0.27	8.08 ± 0.25	8.16 ± 0.27	8 ± 0.32
<i>Variation II</i>	7.41 ± 0.25	7.91 ± 0.2	7.75 ± 0.25	7.75 ± 0.21	8.16 ± 0.24	8.25 ± 0.17
<i>Variation III</i>	7.33 ± 0.33	7.83 ± 0.32	8.25 ± 0.21	7.91 ± 0.33	8.16 ± 0.32	8.33 ± 0.22

Table: 2 Sensory Evaluation of formulated whey water incorporated sugar syrup

<i>Whey water incorporated jaggery syrup</i>	Colour	Appearance	Consistency	Flavour	Taste	Over all Acceptance
<i>Variation I</i>	8.66 ± 0.15	8.73 ± 0.11	8.13 ± 0.25	8.53 ± 0.33	8.46 ± 0.16	8.6 ± 0.23
<i>Variation II</i>	7.46 ± 0.30	7.86 ± 0.16	7.53 ± 0.21	7.6 ± 0.36	7.4 ± 0.32	7.93 ± 0.74
<i>Variation III</i>	7 ± 0.39	7.4 ± 0.25	7.6 ± 0.32	6.9 ± 0.44	7 ± 0.35	7.33 ± 0.33

Table: 3. Sensory Evaluation of formulated whey water incorporated jaggery syrup

<i>Whey water incorporated jaggery syrup</i>	Colour	Appearance	Consistency	Flavour	Taste	Over all Acceptance
<i>Variation I</i>	8.6 ± 0.16	8.46 ± 0.16	7.73 ± 0.28	7.86 ± 0.23	8.2 ± 0.22	8.26 ± 0.20
<i>Variation II</i>	8.26 ± 0.30	8 ± 0.21	8 ± 0.32	8.2 ± 0.27	8.13 ± 0.25	8.33 ± 0.18
<i>Variation III</i>	8.2 ± 0.22	8.13 ± 0.21	8.53 ± 0.29	8.13 ± 0.23	8.53 ± 0.19	8.4 ± 0.23

Table: 4. Sensory Evaluation of formulated whey water incorporated palm jaggery syrup

The sensory parameters like colour, taste, flavor, consistency and appearance were evaluated. The overall mean acceptability and SD for different formulation incorporated with 25%, 50% and 100% are given as follows, for sugar syrup it is 8.04±0.63, 7.8 ± 0.79 and 7.9 ± 0.79 respectively. For jaggery syrup it is 8.5±0.81, 7.6±1.04 and 7.2±1.3 and for palm jaggery syrup, it is 8.1±0.8, 8.1±0.9 and 8.3±0.8. 25% incorporation of whey is more highly acceptable in sensory characteristics, among all the syrups and its values are listed in (Figure 3).

The above (Figure 3) shows the comparison of overall acceptability of different syrups. The acceptability of sugar and palm jaggery syrup increases with increase in the concentration of whey water. This is because in case of sugar syrups are mild

in flavor, while incorporating the whey water, it goes well with the sugar syrup whereas palm jaggery syrup has strong flavors it suppresses the flavor of whey water. Thereby whey water goes well with palm sugar syrup. The acceptability of jaggery syrup decreases with increase in the concentration of whey water, as the syrup becomes sour while incorporating it with whey water. The sugar syrup forms the base for beverages and sweets, it's incorporation with whey water would show significant increase in protein content of the foods.

CONCLUSION

From the present study, it can be concluded that the sugar syrup forms the base for beverages and sweets, it's

incorporation with whey water would show significant increase in protein content of the foods. The incorporation of whey with the natural sweeteners are accepted well among the people

based on its sensory parameters. The samples SV3, JV1, PV3 has the high acceptability rate compared to other samples.

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